

Discovery of Iron Formations (IFs) in Ordovician basin of Eastern Anti Atlas ,Morocco: Nomenclature and Classification.

mohammed charroud and naoufal Saoud

University Mohamed Ben Abdellah Faculty of Sciences and technology, geology, fez, Morocco (mcharroud@hotmail.com)

Discovery of Iron Formations (IFs) in Ordovician basin of Eastern Anti Atlas ,Morocco: Nomenclature and Classification.

Naoufal SAOUD*(1), Mohammed CHARROUD (1), Said HINAJE (1), Mohammed DAHIRE (2), Souhail MOUNIR (1).

1) Laboratory of Georesources and environment, Faculty of Science and Technology, Sidi Mohammed Ben Abdellah University, Fez-Morocco.

2) Laboratory of Geodynamics and natural resources, Faculty of Science Dhar el Mehrez, Sidi Mohammed Ben Abdellah University.

The Tafilalt iron deposit is located in the east part of the Moroccan Anti Atlas structural domain. It is a sedimentary iron ore, deposited during upper ordovician, in shallow sea environment , occasionally influenced by waves, and forwarded to the especial climatic conditions characterizing the Ordovician "earth snowball" event (Saoud et al., 2015 ; El Maazouz, 2007; Hamoumi, 1988). However the Ashgill deglaciation process allows the melting snow on continental areas, which causes an important contribution of sedimentary siliciclastic detrital supply, and a considerable increase of the sea level thus allowing medium oxygenation. In fact, this contributed to the liberation of oxygen which is an essential chemical element for establishing combinations with reduced iron, and giving birth to complex iron oxides, able to gather with the sedimentary siliciclastic fraction. The latter is the phenomenon which promotes the iron oxides precipitation in the Bani2 sandstones, as a form of Hematite (Fe_2O_3) and Magnetite (Fe_3O_4).

The discovery of IF deposit in the Ordovician basin of Tafilalt at the level of the Anti Atlas Moroccan, and their description, illustrates an extension and local character because of its relation with typically geodynamic phenomenon which is the passage from sub-continental glacial medium to marine platform environment. This change is linked to the beginning of the Gondwana migration from an ice polar position to more northern situation (Berry et al., 1990; Destombes et al., 1963, 1966, 1967; Babin et al., 1993; Hamoumi, 1988; EL Mazouz, 2007). The iron content in the Tafilalt IFs is in fact an exploitable ore body, since the tenors exceed 40% (Fe). This syn-sedimentary iron ore is linked to the siliciclastic detrital phase characterizing the Ashgill. It corresponds to an iron deposit of Rapitan type, formed during Upper Ordovician, where the deglaciation is the engine trigger of the iron mineralization establishment.

The petrographic studies and mineralogy of thin sections polished surfaces, prepared from the taken samples, indicate that the mineralization is evolving in a progressive way of the Middle Cambrian, to reach its peak during the upper Ordovician, and it is usually represented in the form of hematite and magnetite, concentrated around the ooides particles, giving rise to a granular or Oolitic iron oxides form.

This iron represented as granular form, is probably caused by the process of super saturation on reduced iron in water column, which can generates a massive extinction of micro-organisms producing the oxygen required for the oxidation of ferrous fraction, and finally precipitates of ferric oxides as an oolitic form.

Through the Tafilalt IFs studies, we have highlighted the distribution of iron mineralization which is, mainly represented as granular or oolitic form. That leaves us classify these formations as "Granular Iron formations" or GIF (Trendal, 2002), which are removed during Neoproterozoic. The Ordovician, " earth snowball" climatic event presents the key factor which had brewed of a very exceptional geographical geodynamic conditions, responsible for the formation of an iron deposit of Type GIF, both assigned to Rapitan kind deposits (Saoud et al. ,2015).

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